

STAGES OF CREATING THE “MED CARD SYSTEM” SOFTWARE PRODUCT FOR USE IN THE MEDICAL FIELD

Khaitbayeva D.Z.

Urgench Branch of Tashkent university of Information Technologies Named After Muhammad al-Khwarizmi

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Abstract. *The field of medicine and information technology is one of the fastest growing areas. The use of information technology in medicine and other fields is also developing rapidly. Much bureaucracy and red tape can be avoided by using IT in the medical field. Waiting in line for hours, a lot of paperwork took up a lot of people's time. Citizens will find it very convenient to use the Medical Card System program that we offer.*

Keywords: *IT, medical, card, System, queue, mobile, program.*

Introduction

In today's world, where medical science and technology continue to advance at an astonishing rate, tracking patient records plays a key role in providing quality and effective medical care. Medical records are an integral part of health, providing a valuable source of information about the health of each patient. In society, the relevance of studying patient medical records is especially acute, given not only the rapid pace of development of medical science and technology, but also a number of challenges facing the healthcare system. This instrument ne tolko obespechivaet nepreryvnost zaboty o zdorove, no i povyshaet bezopasnost pasentiov, sposobstvuet effektivnomu lecheniyu, snijaet izderjki na zdroochranenie i obespechivaet ossov dlya nauchnyx issledovaniy i statisticheskogo analiza. In this chapter, we examine the important role of patient medical record tracking in the modern world, identify the key benefits of this practice, and discuss its role in improving the quality and accessibility of health care.

Research methodology

This field when I was studying in itself exactly that's all similar projects that no we saw And exactly that's all on we worked Chet People in programs that's all similar programs created And their studying We went out alone How many programs we learned they are the following :

Cerner Millennium is a comprehensive health information management system developed by Cerner. Corporation . It provides electronic records and processing of medical data in various medical institutions, such as hospitals, clinics and laboratories. Key features include electronic medical records (EMR) management, patient scheduling, visit scheduling, medical order and prescription management, and data analysis and reporting. The system can also be integrated with other medical systems and devices, such as telemedicine platforms and mobile applications. Despite its many advantages, implementation and support of Cerner Millenniums can be challenging and resource-intensive. High data security standards and compliance with privacy regulations are also required.

ONDOC is a patient health monitoring service with an electronic medical record, recommendations and reminders, telemedicine functionality, as well as a clinic and doctor management system with useful functions and work with clients.

MEDITECH EHR (electronic Health Record is an electronic medical records management platform developed by MEDITECH.

Main Part

The main goal of the project is to create a unified platform for storing and managing patient medical information, which allows you to combine records and diseases from various medical institutions into one centralized database. This makes access to health information more convenient and efficient for patients and medical staff, reducing the risk of relapse and follow-up.

In addition, the system will provide the opportunity to obtain additional information about diseases, including recommendations for treatment and prevention, which will help patients be more informed about their health and make informed decisions about their treatment.

The system also allows you to track pain, identify the dynamics and effectiveness of treatment, which is necessary to improve the work of paramedics and optimize the processes of providing medical care.

An important aspect of the project is also the fight against corruption in the healthcare sector. Since certificates and documents will be issued by the system based on the patient's actual visit to the doctor, this will reduce the opportunities for fraud and illegal obtaining of medical documents, ensuring transparency and reliability of information.

The system is designed taking into account the needs of patients and medical personnel and provides convenient and intuitive access to medical information. For maximum accessibility and convenience, we offer a mobile application for patients, available on iOS and Android, as well as a desktop application for medical staff, supported by various operating systems, including Windows, MacOS and Linux. This approach provides broad user coverage and allows each category of users to effectively manage their medical data and processes.

Mobile app: To ensure that patients have the most convenient and efficient access to their medical information at any time and anywhere, a mobile application will be developed that offers a wide range of functionality. The mobile application provides patients with a simple and intuitive interface that allows them to easily manage their health and medical data. I'll show you the main features and functionality, available and mobile apps that will make the process more accessible and efficient.

Mobile application functionality

OneID system identification : The mobile application offers a convenient and secure way for users to log in and register through OneID system identification. This allows users to quickly and easily access their health information while maintaining a high level of security and privacy.

View Medical History: Patients have the ability to view their complete medical history directly through the mobile application. It can be used for diagnoses, test results, procedures and treatments performed, and other important medical data that helps me stay on top of my health.

View other medical information. After the medical history, the user can also view other medical information. This includes information about blood type, chronic pain, allergies and doctor recommendations. This helps my patients fully understand and manage their health effectively.

Storing medical referrals from a doctor: The application provides a special function for storing medical referrals from a doctor. Patients easily retain the treatment received and easily use it at any convenient time. This facilitates the process of organizing additional surveys and consultations with other residents.

Obtaining online certificates: An important aspect of the mobile application is the ability to obtain official medical certificates and documents online. Patients can request and receive various types of certificates, such as health certificates, test results, medical records and more,

without having to visit a medical facility. This saves time and makes it easier to access vital health information.

Desktop wallpaper

Desktop Application is a powerful tool designed with the physician and medical staff in mind. It has a wide range of functionality and an intuitive interface, and the application provides effective management of medical data and processes and medical institutions. Next, we will look at the key functions and capabilities of the desktop application that make it an integral tool in the work of medical personnel.

Desktop application functionality .

Login with my username and password: Access to the application is provided to medical personnel only with strictly issued credentials, such as login and password issued by the super administrator . This ensures the safety and privacy of medical patients.

Search for a client in the database: The application provides a unique tool for searching for a client in the database of a medical institution. Medical staff can search for a patient, enter their name, identification number and other parameters.

View patient information and medical history: After locating each patient, medical staff can view detailed information about the patient, including their medical history and current health status. This includes self-diagnosis, analysis of results, preliminary treatment with doctors and other important information.

Diagnosis and referral: Physicians are able to screen patients, make diagnoses, and issue referrals for additional testing or treatment, all within a desktop application. This ensures convenience and efficiency in the process of providing medical care.

Difference from other system.

Our health information management system differs from other similar projects in its comprehensive approach and the introduction of advanced technologies in the healthcare field. We do not just offer tools for storing and processing medical data, but strive to create an integrated platform that provides complete control and management of patient health from the beginning to the end of medical processes. Our system is designed keeping in mind the packages and wishes of both patients and medical staff. I provide convenient and intuitive means of accessing and managing health information through mobile and desktop applications. The patient can easily access their medical data and receive online advice and recommendations, allowing them to actively participate in the process of improving their health.

At the same time, our healthcare application provides powerful tools for managing medical data and processes in healthcare organizations. The doctor can provide the patient with the most complete information, make a diagnosis, write prescriptions and create electronic documentation - all in one comfortable and safe environment.

One of the main distinguishing features of our system is an innovative approach to managing medical information. My use of advanced technologies and techniques, such as artificial intelligence and data analytics, to ensure the accuracy, efficiency and security of medical data processing. Thus, the system does not just provide storage and access to medical information, it is a full-fledged tool for improving the processes and mode of medical care, as well as ensuring quality patient care. This significantly simplifies and speeds up the process of providing necessary documents to patients, freeing them from the need to personally visit medical institutions and stand in queues. Patients can easily request and receive various forms of information through mobile or desktop applications, including health information, monitoring results, medical record printouts

and other documents needed for work, school or other purposes. This is especially useful in situations where you need quick access to medical information, such as when visiting another doctor, applying for a job, or signing up for insurance.

Additionally, our app provides user-friendly tools for healthcare professionals. The doctor can easily generate and export the necessary documents directly through the system, which is very economical and improves the process of working with medical documentation.

Thus, the function of online issuance of medical reference books is one of the main differences between our system and other analogue projects, providing convenience, accessibility and efficiency in obtaining and processing medical information.

Conclusion

Based on our research and development, it can be concluded that this desktop application has enormous potential for use in healthcare settings to help improve healthcare delivery processes. Further development and improvement of the application will contribute to further progress in the field of digitalization of healthcare and improve the quality of life of Pasitins.

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